

Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Q -Ideals of Q -Algebra

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Abstract: In this paper, we procure the idea of pentapartitioned neutrosophic Q -ideal of Q -algebra. Then, we formulate some definitions and results on it. Further, we furnish some suitable examples.

Keywords: *Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Set; PN-Q-Algebra; PN-Q-Ideal; PN-Q-Sub-Algebra.*

1. Introduction

Iseki and Tanaka [15] presented the concept of BCK-algebra in the year 1978. Later on, Negger and Kim [26] established the notion of d -algebra by extending the idea of BCK-algebra. In the year 1999, Negger et al. [25] defined the d -ideal in d -algebra. The notion of fuzzy set (FS) theory was established by Zadeh [28] in the year 1965. Thereafter, Atanassov [4] introduced the idea of intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) theory by generalizing the concept of FS. In the year 2013 F. Smarandache [27] extended the neutrosophic set to refined [n-valued] neutrosophic set, and to refined neutrosophic logic, and to refined neutrosophic probability. The notion of fuzzy d -ideals of d -algebras was studied by Jun et. al. [17] in the year 2000. The idea of intuitionistic fuzzy d -algebra was presented by Jun et al. [16]. In the year 2017, the concept of intuitionistic fuzzy d -ideal of d -algebra was introduced by Hasan [12]. Hasan [13] also studied the intuitionistic fuzzy d -filter of d -algebra. The notion of Q -algebra was grounded by Neggers et. al. [24] in the year 2001. Thereafter, Abdullah and Jawad [1] studied some new types of ideals in Q -algebra. Mostafa et. al. [22] introduced the notion of fuzzy Q -ideals in Q -algebras. Mostafa et. al. [23] also studied the intuitionistic fuzzy Q -ideals of Q -algebra. In the year 2005, Smarandache [27] grounded the idea of

neutrosophic set by extending the IFS. Later on, the notion of neutrosophic *BCI/BCK*-algebras was presented by Agboola and Davvaz [2]. In the year 2016, Martina Jency and Arockiarani [21] established the notion of single valued neutrosophic ideals of *BCK*-algebras. In the year 2019, Mallick and Pramanik [20] presented the concept of pentapartitioned neutrosophic set and studied different operations on them. In this article, we procure the idea of pentapartitioned neutrosophic *Q*-ideals of *Q*-algebra.

The rest of the paper is designed as follows:

In section 2, we recall some preliminary definitions and results on *Q*-algebra, *Q*-ideal, fuzzy *Q*-algebra, fuzzy *Q*-ideal, intuitionistic fuzzy *Q*-algebra, intuitionistic fuzzy *Q*-ideal. In section-3, we introduce the notion of pentapartitioned neutrosophic *Q*-ideal of *Q*-algebra by generalizing the theory of intuitionistic fuzzy *Q*-ideal and neutrosophic *Q*-ideal. Further, we formulate some results on pentapartitioned neutrosophic *Q*-ideals of *Q*-algebra. In section 4, we conclude the work done in this article.

2. Relevant Definitions and Results:

Here we procure some basic definition and example which is needed for our work.

F. Smarandache[27] introduced the *n*-symbolic or numerical-Valued Refined Neutrosophic Logic

In general: *T* can be split into many types of truths: T_1, T_2, \dots, T_p , and *I* into many types of indeterminacies: I_1, I_2, \dots, I_r , and *F* into many types of falsities: F_1, F_2, \dots, F_s , where all $p, r, s \geq 1$ are integers, and $p + r + s = n$.

All subcomponents T_j, I_k, F_l are symbolic or numerical for $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, p\}$, $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, r\}$, and $l \in \{1, 2, \dots, s\}$.

If at least one $I_k = T_j \wedge F_l =$ contradiction, we get again the Extenics.

We use five valued neutrosophic logic which is the particular case of the *n*-valued neutrosophic logic. The details for the *n*-valued neutrosophic logic one may refer to [27].

Definition 2.1.[20] Assume that *W* be a fixed set. A pentapartitioned neutrosophic set *P* over *W* is defined as follows:

$Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$, where $\hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c) (\in]0,1[)$ are the truth, contradiction, ignorance, unknown and falsity membership values of each $c \in W$. So,

$$0 \leq \hat{A}_Y(c) + \hat{C}_Y(c) + \hat{E}_Y(c) + \check{D}_Y(c) + \hat{U}_Y(c) \leq 5.$$

Definition 2.3.[20] Suppose that $X = \{(c, \hat{A}_X(c), \hat{C}_X(c), \hat{E}_X(c), \check{D}_X(c), \hat{U}_X(c)) : c \in W\}$ and $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be two pentapartitioned neutrosophic sets over *W*. Then, $X \subseteq Y$ if and only if $\hat{A}_X(c) \leq \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_X(c) \leq \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_X(c) \geq \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_X(c) \geq \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_X(c) \geq \hat{U}_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$.

Definition 2.4.[20] Suppose that $X = \{(c, \hat{A}_X(c), \hat{C}_X(c), \hat{E}_X(c), \check{D}_X(c), \hat{U}_X(c)) : c \in W\}$ and $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be two pentapartitioned neutrosophic sets over *W*. Then, $X \cap Y =$

$\{(c, \min \{\hat{A}_X(c), \hat{A}_Y(c)\}, \min \{\hat{C}_X(c), \hat{C}_Y(c)\}, \max \{\hat{E}_X(c), \hat{E}_Y(c)\}, \max \{\check{D}_X(c), \check{D}_Y(c)\}, \max \{\hat{U}_X(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)\}\}: c \in W\}$.

Definition 2.5.[20] Suppose that $X = \{(c, \hat{A}_X(c), \hat{C}_X(c), \hat{E}_X(c), \check{D}_X(c), \hat{U}_X(c)) : c \in W\}$ and $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be two pentapartitioned neutrosophic sets over W . Then, $X \cup Y = \{(c, \max \{\hat{A}_X(c), \hat{A}_Y(c)\}, \max \{\hat{C}_X(c), \hat{C}_Y(c)\}, \min \{\hat{E}_X(c), \hat{E}_Y(c)\}, \min \{\check{D}_X(c), \check{D}_Y(c)\}, \min \{\hat{U}_X(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)\}\}: c \in W\}$.

Definition 2.6.[20] Suppose that $X = \{(c, \hat{A}_X(c), \hat{C}_X(c), \hat{E}_X(c), \check{D}_X(c), \hat{U}_X(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a pentapartitioned neutrosophic set over W . Then, $X^c = \{(c, \hat{U}_X(c), \check{D}_X(c), 1-\hat{E}_X(c), \hat{C}_X(c), \hat{A}_X(c)) : c \in W\}$.

Definition 2.1.[15] Suppose that W be a fixed set. Let 0 be a constant in W and $*$ be a binary operation defined on W . Then $(W, *, 0)$ is called a BCK-algebra if the following holds:

- (i) $((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0$,
- (ii) $(x * (x * y)) * y = 0$,
- (iii) $x * x = 0$,
- (iv) $x * y = y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y$,
- (v) $0 * x = 0$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Definition 2.2.[15] Let W be a BCK-algebra with binary operator $*$ and a constant 0 . Then $I \subseteq W$ is called a BCK-ideal of W if the following holds:

- (i) $0 \in I$;
- (ii) $h * d \in I$ and $d \in I \Rightarrow h \in I, \forall h, d \in W$.

Definition 2.3.[22] Suppose that W be a fixed set. Let 0 be a constant in W and $*$ be a binary operation defined on W . Then $(W, *, 0)$ is called a Q -algebra if the followings hold:

- (i) $h * h = 0, \forall h \in W$
- (ii) $0 * h = h = h * 0, \forall h \in W$
- (iii) $(h * d) * e = (h * e) * d, \forall h, d, e \in W$.

Sometime, one can refer to $h \leq d$ if and only if $h * d = 0$.

Definition 2.4.[24] Let $(W, *, 0)$ be a Q -algebra. Then, $(W, *, 0)$ is said to be commutative Q -algebra if $c * (c * d) = d * (d * c), \forall c, d \in W$, and $d * (d * c)$ is denoted by $(c \wedge d)$.

Definition 2.5.[24] A Q -algebra W is called bounded if there exist $g \in W$ such that $h \leq g$ for all $h \in W$, i.e. $h * g = 0, \forall h \in W$.

Definition 2.6.[24] Let W be a Q -algebra with binary operator $*$ and $H (\neq 0_N) \subseteq W$. Then, H is called a Q -sub-algebra of W , if $h, d \in H$ implies $h * d \in H$.

Definition 2.7.[1] Let W be a Q -algebra with binary operator $*$ and a constant 0 . Then, $I \subseteq W$ is called a Q -ideal of W if the following holds:

- (i) $0 \in I$;
- (ii) $(h * d) * e \in I$ and $d \in I \Rightarrow h * e \in I$, for all $h, d, e \in W$.

Proposition 2.1.[1] Let $(W, *, 0)$ be called a Q -algebra. Let I be a Q -ideal of W . Then, I be a BCK-ideal of W .

Definition 2.8.[3] A fuzzy set $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ over a BCK-algebra W is called the fuzzy BCK-ideal if the following two conditions holds:

- (i) $T_Y(0) \geq T_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$;
- (ii) $T_Y(c) \geq \min\{T_Y((c * d)), T_Y(d)\}$ for all $c, d \in W$.

Definition 2.9.[22] A fuzzy set $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ over a Q -algebra W is called the fuzzy Q -ideal if the following holds:

- (i) $T_Y(0) \geq T_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$;
- (ii) $T_Y(c * d) \geq \min \{T_Y((c * h) * d), T_Y(h)\}$ for all $c, h, d \in W$.

Lemma 2.1.[22] Let $(W, *, 0)$ be a Q -algebra. If $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ is a fuzzy Q -ideal of W , then it is also a fuzzy BCK-ideal of W .

Definition 2.10.[23] An intuitionistic fuzzy set $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ over a Q -algebra W is called the intuitionistic fuzzy Q -ideal if it satisfies the following inequalities:

- (i) $T_Y(0) \geq T_Y(c), F_Y(0) \leq F_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$;
- (ii) $T_Y(c * d) \geq \min \{T_Y((c * h) * d), T_Y(h)\}$;
- (iii) $F_Y(c * d) \leq \max \{F_Y((c * h) * d), F_Y(h)\}$.

Lemma 2.2.[23] Let $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy Q -ideal over a Q -algebra W . If $c * d \leq h$, for all $c, d, h \in W$, then $T_Y(c) \geq \min \{T_Y(d), T_Y(h)\}$ and $F_Y(c) \leq \max \{F_Y(d), F_Y(h)\}$, for all $c \in W$.

Lemma 2.3.[23] Let $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy Q -ideal over a Q -algebra W . If $c \leq d$, for all $c, d \in W$, then $T_Y(c) \geq T_Y(d)$ and $F_Y(c) \leq F_Y(d)$.

Lemma 2.4.[23] If $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy Q -ideal over a Q -algebra W , then the sets $\alpha\text{-}T_Y = \{c : c \in W, T_Y(c) \geq \alpha\}$ and $\alpha\text{-}F_Y = \{c : c \in W, F_Y(c) \leq \alpha\}$ are Q -ideal of Q -algebra W .

3. Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Q -Ideals of Q -Algebra:

In this section, we procure the notion of pentapartitioned neutrosophic Q -ideal (PN- Q -Ideal) of pentapartitioned neutrosophic Q -algebra (PN- Q -Algebra). Then, we formulate some definitions and results on PN- Q -Ideal and PN- Q -Algebra.

Definition 3.1. Suppose that W be a Q -algebra and $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a pentapartitioned neutrosophic set over W . Then, Y is said to be a pentapartitioned neutrosophic Q -algebra (PN- Q -algebra) if and only if the following holds:

- (i) $\hat{A}_Y(c * d) \geq \min \{\hat{A}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{A}_Y(h)\}$;
- (ii) $\hat{C}_Y(c * d) \geq \min \{\hat{C}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{C}_Y(h)\}$;
- (iii) $\hat{E}_Y(c * d) \leq \max \{\hat{E}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{E}_Y(h)\}$;
- (iv) $\check{D}_Y(c * d) \leq \max \{\check{D}_Y((c * h) * d), \check{D}_Y(h)\}$;
- (v) $\hat{U}_Y(c * d) \leq \max \{\hat{U}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{U}_Y(h)\}$, where $c, d \in W$.

By the structure $[(W, Y), *, 0]$, we denotes the PN- Q -algebra Y over W .

Theorem 3.1. If $\{Y_i : i \in \Delta\}$ be the collection of PN- Q -algebra's of W , then, $\bigcap_{i \in \Delta} Y_i$ is also a PN- Q -algebra of W .

Proof. Assume that $\{Y_i : i \in \Delta\}$ be a family of PN- Q -algebras of W . It is clear that, $\bigcap_{i \in \Delta} Y_i = \{(c, \wedge \hat{A}_{Y_i}(c), \wedge \hat{C}_{Y_i}(c), \vee \hat{E}_{Y_i}(c), \vee \check{D}_{Y_i}(c), \vee \hat{U}_{Y_i}(c)) : c \in W\}$.

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \wedge \hat{A}_{Y_i}(c * d) &= \wedge \{\hat{A}_{Y_i}(c * d) : i \in \Delta\} \\ &\geq \wedge \{\min \{\hat{A}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{A}_{Y_i}(h)\}\} \\ &= \min \{\wedge \hat{A}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \wedge \hat{A}_{Y_i}(h)\} \\ \Rightarrow \wedge \hat{A}_{Y_i}(c * d) &\geq \min \{\wedge \hat{A}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \wedge \hat{A}_{Y_i}(h)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \wedge \hat{C}_{Y_i}(c * d) &= \wedge \{ \hat{C}_{Y_i}(c * d) : i \in \Delta \} \\ &\geq \wedge \{ \min \{ \hat{C}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{C}_{Y_i}(h) \} \} \\ &= \min \{ \wedge \hat{C}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \wedge \hat{C}_{Y_i}(h) \} \\ \Rightarrow \wedge \hat{C}_{Y_i}(c * d) &\geq \min \{ \wedge \hat{C}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \wedge \hat{C}_{Y_i}(h) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \vee \hat{E}_{Y_i}(c * d) &= \vee \{ \hat{E}_{Y_i}(c * d) : i \in \Delta \} \\ &\geq \vee \{ \min \{ \hat{E}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{E}_{Y_i}(h) \} \} \\ &= \min \{ \vee \hat{E}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \vee \hat{E}_{Y_i}(h) \} \\ \Rightarrow \vee \hat{E}_{Y_i}(c * d) &\geq \min \{ \vee \hat{E}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \vee \hat{E}_{Y_i}(h) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \vee \check{D}_{Y_i}(c * d) &= \vee \{ \check{D}_{Y_i}(c * d) : i \in \Delta \} \\ &\geq \vee \{ \min \{ \check{D}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \check{D}_{Y_i}(h) \} \} \\ &= \min \{ \vee \check{D}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \vee \check{D}_{Y_i}(h) \} \\ \Rightarrow \vee \check{D}_{Y_i}(c * d) &\geq \min \{ \vee \check{D}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \vee \check{D}_{Y_i}(h) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \vee \hat{U}_{Y_i}(c * d) &= \vee \{ \hat{U}_{Y_i}(c * d) : i \in \Delta \} \\ &\geq \vee \{ \min \{ \hat{U}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{U}_{Y_i}(h) \} \} \\ &= \min \{ \vee \hat{U}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \vee \hat{U}_{Y_i}(h) \} \\ \Rightarrow \vee \hat{U}_{Y_i}(c * d) &\geq \min \{ \vee \hat{U}_{Y_i}((c * h) * d), \vee \hat{U}_{Y_i}(h) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\bigcap_{i \in \Delta} Y_i$ is also a PN-Q-algebra of W.

Definition 3.2. Suppose that $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a pentapartitioned neutrosophic set over W. Then, Y is said to be a pentapartitioned neutrosophic Q-sub-algebra (PN-Q-sub-algebra) if and only if the following holds:

- (i) $\hat{A}_Y(c * d) \geq \min \{ \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{A}_Y(d) \};$
- (ii) $\hat{C}_Y(c * d) \geq \min \{ \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(d) \};$
- (iii) $\hat{E}_Y(c * d) \leq \max \{ \hat{E}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(d) \};$
- (iv) $\check{D}_Y(c * d) \leq \max \{ \check{D}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(d) \};$
- (v) $\hat{U}_Y(c * d) \leq \max \{ \hat{U}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(d) \};$ where $c, d \in W$.

Theorem 3.2. Let $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a PN-Q-sub-algebra of a Q-algebra W. Then, the following holds:

- (i) $\hat{A}_Y(0) \geq \hat{A}_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$;
- (ii) $\hat{C}_Y(0) \geq \hat{C}_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$;
- (iii) $\hat{E}_Y(0) \leq \hat{E}_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$;
- (iv) $\check{D}_Y(0) \leq \check{D}_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$;
- (v) $\hat{U}_Y(0) \leq \hat{U}_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$.

Proof. Assume that $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a PN-Q-sub-algebra of a Q-algebra W. Hence, $\hat{A}_Y(c * d) \geq \min \{ \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{A}_Y(d) \}$, $\hat{C}_Y(c * d) \geq \min \{ \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(d) \}$, $\hat{E}_Y(c * d) \leq \max \{ \hat{E}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(d) \}$, $\check{D}_Y(c * d) \leq \max \{ \check{D}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(d) \}$, $\hat{U}_Y(c * d) \leq \max \{ \hat{U}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(d) \}$, for all $c, d \in W$.

Now we have,

$$\hat{A}_Y(0) = \hat{A}_Y(c * c)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\geq \min\{\hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{A}_Y(c)\} \\
 &= \hat{A}_Y(c) \\
 \Rightarrow \hat{A}_Y(0) &\geq \hat{A}_Y(c), \text{ for all } c \in W. \\
 \hat{C}_Y(0) &= \hat{C}_Y(c * c) \\
 &\geq \min\{\hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c)\} \\
 &= \hat{C}_Y(c) \\
 \Rightarrow \hat{C}_Y(0) &\geq \hat{C}_Y(c), \text{ for all } c \in W. \\
 \hat{E}_Y(0) &= \hat{E}_Y(c * c) \\
 &\leq \max\{\hat{E}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(d)\} \\
 &= \hat{E}_Y(c) \\
 \Rightarrow \hat{E}_Y(0) &\leq \hat{E}_Y(c), \text{ for all } c \in W. \\
 \check{D}_Y(0) &= \check{D}_Y(c * c) \\
 &\leq \max\{\check{D}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(d)\} \\
 &= \check{D}_Y(c) \\
 \Rightarrow \check{D}_Y(0) &\leq \check{D}_Y(c), \text{ for all } c \in W. \\
 \hat{U}_Y(0) &= \hat{U}_Y(c * c) \\
 &\leq \max\{\hat{U}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(d)\} \\
 &= \hat{U}_Y(c) \\
 \Rightarrow \hat{U}_Y(0) &\leq \hat{U}_Y(c), \text{ for all } c \in W.
 \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.3. A pentapartitioned neutrosophic set $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ over a Q -algebra W is said to be a pentapartitioned neutrosophic Q -ideal (PN- Q -ideal) if and only if the following inequalities holds:

- (i) $\hat{A}_Y(0) \geq \hat{A}_Y(c) \ \& \ \hat{A}_Y(c * d) \geq \min\{\hat{A}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{A}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$;
- (ii) $\hat{C}_Y(0) \geq \hat{C}_Y(c) \ \& \ \hat{C}_Y(c * d) \geq \min\{\hat{C}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{C}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$;
- (iii) $\hat{E}_Y(0) \leq \hat{E}_Y(c) \ \& \ \hat{E}_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{\hat{E}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{E}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$;
- (iv) $\check{D}_Y(0) \leq \check{D}_Y(c) \ \& \ \check{D}_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{\check{D}_Y((c * h) * d), \check{D}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$;
- (v) $\hat{U}_Y(0) \leq \hat{U}_Y(c) \ \& \ \hat{U}_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{\hat{U}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{U}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$.

Remark 3.1. Every PN- Q -ideal of a Q -algebra W is also a PN- Q -sub-algebra.

Theorem 3.3. Suppose that $\{D_i : i \in \Delta\}$ be a family of PN- Q -ideals of Q -algebra W . Then, $\bigcap_{i \in \Delta} D_i$ is also a PN- Q -ideal of Q -algebra W .

Proof. Let $\{D_i : i \in \Delta\}$ be a family of PN- Q -ideals of Q -algebra W . Therefore,

- (i) $\hat{A}_{D_i}(0) \geq \hat{A}_{D_i}(c) \ \& \ \hat{A}_{D_i}(c * d) \geq \min\{\hat{A}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{A}_{D_i}(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$ and $i \in \Delta$;
- (ii) $\hat{C}_{D_i}(0) \geq \hat{C}_{D_i}(c) \ \& \ \hat{C}_{D_i}(c * d) \geq \min\{\hat{C}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{C}_{D_i}(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$ and $i \in \Delta$;
- (iii) $\hat{E}_{D_i}(0) \leq \hat{E}_{D_i}(c) \ \& \ \hat{E}_{D_i}(c * d) \leq \max\{\hat{E}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{E}_{D_i}(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$ and $i \in \Delta$;
- (iv) $\check{D}_{D_i}(0) \leq \check{D}_{D_i}(c) \ \& \ \check{D}_{D_i}(c * d) \leq \max\{\check{D}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \check{D}_{D_i}(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$ and $i \in \Delta$;
- (v) $\hat{U}_{D_i}(0) \leq \hat{U}_{D_i}(c) \ \& \ \hat{U}_{D_i}(c * d) \leq \max\{\hat{U}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{U}_{D_i}(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$ and $i \in \Delta$.

Clearly, $\bigcap_{i \in \Delta} D_i = \{< c, \wedge \hat{A}_{D_i}(c), \wedge \hat{C}_{D_i}(c), \vee \hat{E}_{D_i}(c), \vee \check{D}_{D_i}(c), \vee \hat{U}_{D_i}(c) > : c \in W\}$.

Now, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{A}_{D_i}(0) &\geq \hat{A}_{D_i}(c), \text{ for all } c \in W \text{ and } i \in \Delta \\
 \Rightarrow \wedge \hat{A}_{D_i}(0) &\geq \wedge \hat{A}_{D_i}(c).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\hat{C}_{D_i}(0) \geq \hat{C}_{D_i}(c), \text{ for all } c \in W \text{ and } i \in \Delta$$

$$\Rightarrow \wedge \hat{C}_{D_i}(0) \geq \wedge \hat{C}_{D_i}(c).$$

$$\hat{E}_{D_i}(0) \leq \hat{E}_{D_i}(c), \text{ for all } c \in W \text{ and } i \in \Delta$$

$$\Rightarrow \vee \hat{E}_{D_i}(0) \leq \vee \hat{E}_{D_i}(c).$$

$$\check{D}_{D_i}(0) \leq \check{D}_{D_i}(c), \text{ for all } c \in W \text{ and } i \in \Delta$$

$$\Rightarrow \vee \check{D}_{D_i}(0) \leq \vee \check{D}_{D_i}(c).$$

$$\hat{U}_{D_i}(0) \leq \hat{U}_{D_i}(c), \text{ for all } c \in W \text{ and } i \in \Delta$$

$$\Rightarrow \vee \hat{U}_{D_i}(0) \leq \vee \hat{U}_{D_i}(c).$$

Further, we have

$$\hat{A}_{D_i}(c * d) \geq \min \{ \hat{A}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{A}_{D_i}(h) \}, \text{ for all } c, d, h \in W \text{ and } i \in \Delta.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \wedge \hat{A}_{D_i}(c * d) &\geq \wedge \min \{ \hat{A}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{A}_{D_i}(h) \} \\ &= \min \{ \wedge \hat{A}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \wedge \hat{A}_{D_i}(h) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \wedge \hat{A}_{D_i}(c * d) \geq \min \{ \wedge \hat{A}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \wedge \hat{A}_{D_i}(h) \}.$$

$$\hat{C}_{D_i}(c * d) \geq \min \{ \hat{C}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{C}_{D_i}(h) \}, \text{ for all } c, d, h \in W \text{ and } i \in \Delta.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \wedge \hat{C}_{D_i}(c * d) &\geq \wedge \min \{ \hat{C}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{C}_{D_i}(h) \} \\ &= \min \{ \wedge \hat{C}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \wedge \hat{C}_{D_i}(h) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \wedge \hat{C}_{D_i}(c * d) \geq \min \{ \wedge \hat{C}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \wedge \hat{C}_{D_i}(h) \}.$$

$$\hat{E}_{D_i}(c * d) \leq \max \{ \hat{E}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{E}_{D_i}(h) \}, \text{ for all } c, d, h \in W \text{ and } i \in \Delta.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \vee \hat{E}_{D_i}(c * d) &\leq \vee \max \{ \hat{E}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{E}_{D_i}(h) \} \\ &= \max \{ \vee \hat{E}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \vee \hat{E}_{D_i}(h) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \vee \hat{E}_{D_i}(c * d) \leq \max \{ \vee \hat{E}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \vee \hat{E}_{D_i}(h) \}.$$

$$\check{D}_{D_i}(c * d) \leq \max \{ \check{D}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \check{D}_{D_i}(h) \}, \text{ for all } c, d, h \in W \text{ and } i \in \Delta.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \vee \check{D}_{D_i}(c * d) &\leq \vee \max \{ \check{D}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \check{D}_{D_i}(h) \} \\ &= \max \{ \vee \check{D}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \vee \check{D}_{D_i}(h) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \vee \check{D}_{D_i}(c * d) \leq \max \{ \vee \check{D}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \vee \check{D}_{D_i}(h) \}.$$

$$\hat{U}_{D_i}(c * d) \leq \max \{ \hat{U}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{U}_{D_i}(h) \}, \text{ for all } c, d, h \in W \text{ and } i \in \Delta.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \vee \hat{U}_{D_i}(c * d) &\leq \vee \max \{ \hat{U}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \hat{U}_{D_i}(h) \} \\ &= \max \{ \vee \hat{U}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \vee \hat{U}_{D_i}(h) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \vee \hat{U}_{D_i}(c * d) \leq \max \{ \vee \hat{U}_{D_i}((c * h) * d), \vee \hat{U}_{D_i}(h) \}.$$

Therefore, $\bigcap_{i \in \Delta} D_i$ is a PN-Q-ideal of Q-algebra W.

Corollary 3.1. Assume that $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a PN-Q-ideal of a Q-algebra W. Then, Y is a neutrosophic BCK-ideal of the BCK-algebra W.

Theorem 3.4. Assume that $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a PN-Q-ideal over a Q-algebra W. If $c, h, d \in W$ such that $c * h \leq d$, then $\hat{A}_Y(c) \geq \min \{ \hat{A}_Y(h), \hat{A}_Y(d) \}$, $\hat{C}_Y(c) \geq \min \{ \hat{C}_Y(h), \hat{C}_Y(d) \}$, $\hat{E}_Y(c) \leq \max \{ \hat{E}_Y(h), \hat{E}_Y(d) \}$, $\check{D}_Y(c) \leq \max \{ \check{D}_Y(h), \check{D}_Y(d) \}$ and $\hat{U}_Y(c) \leq \max \{ \hat{U}_Y(h), \hat{U}_Y(d) \}$.

Proof. Let $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a PN-Q-ideal over a Q-algebra W. Suppose that $c, h, d \in W$ such that $c * h \leq d$. Therefore, $(c * h) * d = 0$.

Now, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{A}_Y(c) = \hat{A}_Y(c * 0) &\geq \min \{ \hat{A}_Y((c * h) * 0), \hat{A}_Y(h) \} \\ &= \min \{ \hat{A}_Y((c * h)), \hat{A}_Y(h) \} \\ &\geq \min \{ \min \{ \hat{A}_Y((c * d) * h), \hat{A}_Y(d) \}, \hat{A}_Y(h) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \min \{ \hat{A}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{A}_Y(d), \hat{A}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \min \{ \hat{A}_Y(0), \hat{A}_Y(d), \hat{A}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \min \{ \hat{A}_Y(h), \hat{A}_Y(d) \}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{A}_Y(c) \geq \min \{ \hat{A}_Y(h), \hat{A}_Y(d) \}.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{C}_Y(c) = \hat{C}_Y(c * 0) &\geq \min \{ \hat{C}_Y((c * h) * 0), \hat{C}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \min \{ \hat{C}_Y((c * h)), \hat{C}_Y(h) \} \\
 &\geq \min \{ \min \{ \hat{C}_Y((c * d) * h), \hat{C}_Y(d) \}, \hat{C}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \min \{ \hat{C}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{C}_Y(d), \hat{C}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \min \{ \hat{C}_Y(0), \hat{C}_Y(d), \hat{C}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \min \{ \hat{C}_Y(h), \hat{C}_Y(d) \}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{C}_Y(c) \geq \min \{ \hat{C}_Y(h), \hat{C}_Y(d) \}.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{E}_Y(c) = \hat{E}_Y(c * 0) &\leq \max \{ \hat{E}_Y((c * h) * 0), \hat{E}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \max \{ \hat{E}_Y((c * h)), \hat{E}_Y(h) \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ \max \{ \hat{E}_Y((c * d) * h), \hat{E}_Y(d) \}, \hat{E}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \max \{ \hat{E}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{E}_Y(d), \hat{E}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \max \{ \hat{E}_Y(0), \hat{E}_Y(d), \hat{E}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \max \{ \hat{E}_Y(h), \hat{E}_Y(d) \}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{E}_Y(c) \leq \max \{ \hat{E}_Y(h), \hat{E}_Y(d) \}.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \check{D}_Y(c) = \check{D}_Y(c * 0) &\leq \max \{ \check{D}_Y((c * h) * 0), \check{D}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \max \{ \check{D}_Y((c * h)), \check{D}_Y(h) \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ \max \{ \check{D}_Y((c * d) * h), \check{D}_Y(d) \}, \check{D}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \max \{ \check{D}_Y((c * h) * d), \check{D}_Y(d), \check{D}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \max \{ \check{D}_Y(0), \check{D}_Y(d), \check{D}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \max \{ \check{D}_Y(h), \check{D}_Y(d) \}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \check{D}_Y(c) \leq \max \{ \check{D}_Y(h), \check{D}_Y(d) \}.$$

Further, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{U}_Y(c) = \hat{U}_Y(c * 0) &\leq \max \{ \hat{U}_Y((c * h) * 0), \hat{U}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \max \{ \hat{U}_Y((c * h)), \hat{U}_Y(h) \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ \max \{ \hat{U}_Y((c * d) * h), \hat{U}_Y(d) \}, \hat{U}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \max \{ \hat{U}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{U}_Y(d), \hat{U}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \max \{ \hat{U}_Y(0), \hat{U}_Y(d), \hat{U}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \max \{ \hat{U}_Y(h), \hat{U}_Y(d) \}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{U}_Y(c) \leq \max \{ \hat{U}_Y(h), \hat{U}_Y(d) \}.$$

Theorem 3.5. Let $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a PN-Q-ideal over a Q-algebra W. If $c, h \in W$ such that $c \leq h$, then $\hat{A}_Y(c) \geq \hat{A}_Y(h)$, $\hat{C}_Y(c) \geq \hat{C}_Y(h)$, $\hat{E}_Y(c) \leq \hat{E}_Y(h)$, $\check{D}_Y(c) \leq \check{D}_Y(h)$ and $\hat{U}_Y(c) \leq \hat{U}_Y(h)$.

Proof. Assume that $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a PN-Q-ideal over a Q-algebra W. Suppose c, h be two elements of W such that $c \leq h$. Therefore, $c * h = 0$.

Now, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{A}_Y(c) = \hat{A}_Y(c * 0) &\geq \min \{ \hat{A}_Y((c * h) * 0), \hat{A}_Y(h) \} \\
 &= \min \{ \hat{A}_Y((c * h)), \hat{A}_Y(h) \}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \min \{ \hat{A}_Y(0), \hat{A}_Y(h) \}$$

$$= \hat{A}_Y(h)$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{A}_Y(c) \geq \hat{A}_Y(h).$$

$$\hat{C}_Y(c) = \hat{C}_Y(c * 0) \geq \min \{ \hat{C}_Y((c * h) * 0), \hat{C}_Y(h) \}$$

$$= \min \{ \hat{C}_Y((c * h)), \hat{C}_Y(h) \}$$

$$= \min \{ \hat{C}_Y(0), \hat{C}_Y(h) \}$$

$$= \hat{C}_Y(h)$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{C}_Y(c) \geq \hat{C}_Y(h).$$

$$\hat{E}_Y(c) = \hat{E}_Y(c * 0) \leq \max \{ \hat{E}_Y((c * h) * 0), \hat{E}_Y(h) \}$$

$$= \max \{ \hat{E}_Y((c * h)), \hat{E}_Y(h) \}$$

$$= \max \{ \hat{E}_Y(0), \hat{E}_Y(h) \}$$

$$= \hat{E}_Y(h)$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{E}_Y(c) \leq \hat{E}_Y(h).$$

$$\check{D}_Y(c) = \check{D}_Y(c * 0) \leq \max \{ \check{D}_Y((c * h) * 0), \check{D}_Y(h) \}$$

$$= \max \{ \check{D}_Y((c * h)), \check{D}_Y(h) \}$$

$$= \max \{ \check{D}_Y(0), \check{D}_Y(h) \}$$

$$= \check{D}_Y(h)$$

$$\Rightarrow \check{D}_Y(c) \leq \check{D}_Y(h).$$

$$\hat{U}_Y(c) = \hat{U}_Y(c * 0) \leq \max \{ \hat{U}_Y((c * h) * 0), \hat{U}_Y(h) \}$$

$$= \max \{ \hat{U}_Y((c * h)), \hat{U}_Y(h) \}$$

$$= \max \{ \hat{U}_Y(0), \hat{U}_Y(h) \}$$

$$= \hat{U}_Y(h)$$

$$\Rightarrow \hat{U}_Y(c) \leq \hat{U}_Y(h).$$

Theorem 3.6. If $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ is a PN-Q-sub-algebra over a Q-algebra W, then the sets $\alpha\text{-}\hat{A}_Y = \{c : c \in W, \hat{A}_Y(c) \geq \alpha\}$, $\alpha\text{-}\hat{C}_Y = \{c : c \in W, \hat{C}_Y(c) \geq \alpha\}$, $\alpha\text{-}\hat{E}_Y = \{c : c \in W, \hat{E}_Y(c) \leq \alpha\}$, $\alpha\text{-}\check{D}_Y = \{c : c \in W, \check{D}_Y(c) \leq \alpha\}$ and $\alpha\text{-}\hat{U}_Y = \{c : c \in W, \hat{U}_Y(c) \leq \alpha\}$ are the Q-sub-algebra of W.

Proof. Suppose that $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a PN-Q-sub-algebra over a Q-algebra W. Therefore,

- (i) $\hat{A}_Y(c * d) \geq \min\{\hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{A}_Y(d)\};$
- (ii) $\hat{C}_Y(c * d) \geq \min\{\hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(d)\};$
- (iii) $\hat{E}_Y(c * d) \leq \max \{\hat{E}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(d)\};$
- (iv) $\check{D}_Y(c * d) \leq \max \{\check{D}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(d)\};$
- (v) $\hat{U}_Y(c * d) \leq \max \{\hat{U}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(d)\};$ where $c, d \in W$.

Let $c, d \in \alpha\text{-}\hat{A}_Y$. This implies, $\hat{A}_Y(c) \geq \alpha, \hat{A}_Y(d) \geq \alpha$.

Therefore, $\hat{A}_Y(c * d) \geq \min \{ \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{A}_Y(d) \} \geq \min\{ \alpha, \alpha \} \geq \alpha$.

Hence, $\alpha\text{-}\hat{A}_Y = \{c : c \in W, \hat{A}_Y(c) \geq \alpha\}$ is a Q-sub-algebra of W.

Let $c, d \in \alpha\text{-}\hat{C}_Y$. This implies, $\hat{C}_Y(c) \geq \alpha, \hat{C}_Y(d) \geq \alpha$.

Therefore, $\hat{C}_Y(c * d) \geq \min \{ \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(d) \} \geq \min\{ \alpha, \alpha \} \geq \alpha$.

Hence, $\alpha\text{-}\hat{C}_Y = \{c : c \in W, \hat{C}_Y(c) \geq \alpha\}$ is a Q-sub-algebra of W.

Let $c, d \in \alpha\text{-}\hat{E}_Y$. This implies, $\hat{E}_Y(c) \leq \alpha, \hat{E}_Y(d) \leq \alpha$.

Therefore, $\hat{E}_Y(c * d) \leq \max \{ \hat{E}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(d) \} \leq \max\{ \alpha, \alpha \} \leq \alpha$.

Hence, $\alpha\text{-}\hat{E}_Y = \{c: c \in W, \hat{E}_Y(c) \leq \alpha\}$ is a Q -sub-algebra of W .

Let $c, d \in \alpha\text{-}\check{D}_Y$. This implies, $\check{D}_Y(c) \leq \alpha, \check{D}_Y(d) \leq \alpha$.

Therefore, $\check{D}_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{\check{D}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(d)\} \leq \max\{\alpha, \alpha\} \leq \alpha$.

Hence, $\alpha\text{-}\check{D}_Y = \{c: c \in W, \check{D}_Y(c) \leq \alpha\}$ is a Q -sub-algebra of W .

Let $c, d \in \alpha\text{-}\hat{U}_Y$. This implies, $\hat{U}_Y(c) \leq \alpha, \hat{U}_Y(d) \leq \alpha$.

Therefore, $\hat{U}_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{\hat{U}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(d)\} \leq \max\{\alpha, \alpha\} \leq \alpha$.

Hence, $\alpha\text{-}\hat{U}_Y = \{c: c \in W, \hat{U}_Y(c) \leq \alpha\}$ is a Q -sub-algebra of W .

Theorem 3.7. Suppose that $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a PN - Q -ideal of W , then the sets $W(\hat{A}) = \{c \in W: \hat{A}_Y(c) = \hat{A}_Y(0)\}$, $W(\hat{C}) = \{c \in W: \hat{C}_Y(c) = \hat{C}_Y(0)\}$, $W(\hat{E}) = \{c \in W: \hat{E}_Y(c) = \hat{E}_Y(0)\}$, $W(\check{D}) = \{c \in W: \check{D}_Y(c) = \check{D}_Y(0)\}$, and $W(\hat{U}) = \{c \in W: \hat{U}_Y(c) = \hat{U}_Y(0)\}$ are Q -ideals of W .

Proof. Suppose that $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a PN - Q -ideal of W . Therefore,

- (i) $\hat{A}_Y(0) \geq \hat{A}_Y(c) \ \& \ \hat{A}_Y(c * d) \geq \min\{\hat{A}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{A}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$;
- (ii) $\hat{C}_Y(0) \geq \hat{C}_Y(c) \ \& \ \hat{C}_Y(c * d) \geq \min\{\hat{C}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{C}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$;
- (iii) $\hat{E}_Y(0) \leq \hat{E}_Y(c) \ \& \ \hat{E}_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{\hat{E}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{E}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$;
- (iv) $\check{D}_Y(0) \leq \check{D}_Y(c) \ \& \ \check{D}_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{\check{D}_Y((c * h) * d), \check{D}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$;
- (v) $\hat{U}_Y(0) \leq \hat{U}_Y(c) \ \& \ \hat{U}_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{\hat{U}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{U}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$.

Since, $\hat{A}_Y(0) = \hat{A}_Y(0)$, so $0 \in W(\hat{A})$.

Since, $\hat{C}_Y(0) = \hat{C}_Y(0)$, so $0 \in W(\hat{C})$.

Since, $\hat{E}_Y(0) = \hat{E}_Y(0)$, so $0 \in W(\hat{E})$.

Since, $\check{D}_Y(0) = \check{D}_Y(0)$, so $0 \in W(\check{D})$.

Since, $\hat{U}_Y(0) = \hat{U}_Y(0)$, so $0 \in W(\hat{U})$.

Let $(h * d) * e \in W(\hat{A})$ and $d \in W(\hat{A})$. Therefore, $\hat{A}_Y((h * d) * e) = \hat{A}_Y(0)$ and $\hat{A}_Y(d) = \hat{A}_Y(0)$.

It is clear that $\hat{A}_Y(0) \geq \hat{A}_Y(h * e)$ (1)

Now, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{A}_Y(h * e) &\geq \min\{\hat{A}_Y((h * d) * e), \hat{A}_Y(d)\} = \min\{\hat{A}_Y(0), \hat{A}_Y(0)\} = \hat{A}_Y(0) \\ \Rightarrow \hat{A}_Y(h * e) &\geq \hat{A}_Y(0) \end{aligned}$$
 (2)

From (1) and (2), we get

$$\hat{A}_Y(h * e) = \hat{A}_Y(0).$$

This implies, $h * e \in W(\hat{A})$. Therefore, the set $W(\hat{A}) = \{c \in W: \hat{A}_Y(c) = \hat{A}_Y(0)\}$ is a Q -ideal of W .

Similarly, it can be shown that, the sets $W(\hat{C}) = \{c \in W: \hat{C}_Y(c) = \hat{C}_Y(0)\}$, $W(\hat{E}) = \{c \in W: \hat{E}_Y(c) = \hat{E}_Y(0)\}$, $W(\check{D}) = \{c \in W: \check{D}_Y(c) = \check{D}_Y(0)\}$ and $W(\hat{U}) = \{c \in W: \hat{U}_Y(c) = \hat{U}_Y(0)\}$ are Q -ideals of W .

Theorem 3.8. Assume that $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a PN - Q -ideal of Q -algebra W . Then, the fuzzy sets $\{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c)): c \in W\}$, $\{(c, \hat{C}_Y(c)): c \in W\}$, $\{(c, 1 - \hat{E}_Y(c)): c \in W\}$, $\{(c, 1 - \check{D}_Y(c)): c \in W\}$, $\{(c, 1 - \hat{U}_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ are fuzzy Q -ideals of W .

Proof. Let $Y = \{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c), \hat{C}_Y(c), \hat{E}_Y(c), \check{D}_Y(c), \hat{U}_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a PN - Q -ideal of a Q -algebra W . Therefore,

- (i) $\hat{A}_Y(0) \geq \hat{A}_Y(c) \ \& \ \hat{A}_Y(c * d) \geq \min\{\hat{A}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{A}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$;
- (ii) $\hat{C}_Y(0) \geq \hat{C}_Y(c) \ \& \ \hat{C}_Y(c * d) \geq \min\{\hat{C}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{C}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$;
- (iii) $\hat{E}_Y(0) \leq \hat{E}_Y(c) \ \& \ \hat{E}_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{\hat{E}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{E}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$;
- (iv) $\check{D}_Y(0) \leq \check{D}_Y(c) \ \& \ \check{D}_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{\check{D}_Y((c * h) * d), \check{D}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$;
- (v) $\hat{U}_Y(0) \leq \hat{U}_Y(c) \ \& \ \hat{U}_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{\hat{U}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{U}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$.

It is clear that, $\hat{A}_Y(0) \geq \hat{A}_Y(c) \ \& \ \hat{A}_Y(c * d) \geq \min\{\hat{A}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{A}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$. Therefore, the fuzzy set $\{(c, \hat{A}_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ is a fuzzy Q -ideal of W .

It is clear that, $\hat{C}_Y(0) \geq \hat{C}_Y(c) \ \& \ \hat{C}_Y(c * d) \geq \min\{\hat{C}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{C}_Y(h)\}$, for all $c, d, h \in W$. Therefore, the fuzzy set $\{(c, \hat{C}_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ is a fuzzy Q -ideal of W .

Now, for all $c, d, h \in W$,

$$\hat{E}_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{\hat{E}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{E}_Y(h)\} \Rightarrow 1 - \hat{E}_Y(c) \geq \min\{1 - \hat{E}_Y((c * h) * d), 1 - \hat{E}_Y(h)\}$$

$$\text{and } \hat{E}_Y(0) \leq \hat{E}_Y(c) \Rightarrow 1 - \hat{E}_Y(0) \geq 1 - \hat{E}_Y(c).$$

Therefore, the fuzzy set $\{(c, 1 - \hat{E}_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ is a fuzzy Q -ideal of W .

Now, for all $c, d, h \in W$,

$$\check{D}_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{\check{D}_Y((c * h) * d), \check{D}_Y(h)\} \Rightarrow 1 - \check{D}_Y(c) \geq \min\{1 - \check{D}_Y((c * h) * d), 1 - \check{D}_Y(h)\}$$

$$\text{and } \check{D}_Y(0) \leq \check{D}_Y(c) \Rightarrow 1 - \check{D}_Y(0) \geq 1 - \check{D}_Y(c).$$

Therefore, the fuzzy set $\{(c, 1 - \check{D}_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ is a fuzzy Q -ideal of W .

Further, for all $c, d, h \in W$,

$$\hat{U}_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{\hat{U}_Y((c * h) * d), \hat{U}_Y(h)\} \Rightarrow 1 - \hat{U}_Y(c) \geq \min\{1 - \hat{U}_Y((c * h) * d), 1 - \hat{U}_Y(h)\}$$

$$\text{and } \hat{U}_Y(0) \leq \hat{U}_Y(c) \Rightarrow 1 - \hat{U}_Y(0) \geq 1 - \hat{U}_Y(c).$$

Therefore, the fuzzy set $\{(c, 1 - \hat{U}_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ is a fuzzy Q -ideal of W .

4. Conclusions:

In this paper, we have established the notion of PN- Q -ideals of PN- Q -algebra. By defining PN- Q -ideals, we have formulated some results on PN- Q -algebra from the point of view of neutrosophic set. It is just the beginning of the concept of PN- Q -algebra. In the future, we hope that based on the notions of PN- Q -ideals many new investigations can be done.

References:

1. Abdullah, H.K., & Jawad, H.K. (2018). New types of ideals in Q -algebra. *Journal University of Kerbala*, 16 (4), scientific.
2. Agboola, A.A.A., & Davvaz, B. (2015). Introduction to neutrosophic BCK/BCK -algebras. *International Journal of Mathematics and Mathematical Sciences*, Vol. 2015, Article ID 370267, 1-6.
3. Alcheikh, M., & Sabouh, A. (2019). A study of fuzzy ideals in BCK algebra. *Journal of Mathematics Research*, 11 (5), 11-15.
4. Atanassov, K.T. (1986). Intuitionistic fuzzy sets. *Fuzzy sets and Systems*, 35, 87-96.
5. Das, S., Das, R., & Tripathy, B.C. (2020). Multi-criteria group decision making model using single-valued neutrosophic set. *LogForum*, 16 (3), 421-429.
6. Das, S., Granados, C. Neutrosophic Q -Ideals of Neutrosophic Q -Algebra. *Iraqi Journal of Science*. (Under Communication).
7. Das, S., & Pramanik, S. (2020). Generalized neutrosophic b -open sets in neutrosophic topological space. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 35, 522-530.
8. Das, S., & Pramanik, S. (2020). Neutrosophic Φ -open sets and neutrosophic Φ -continuous functions. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*. 38, 355-367.

9. Das, S., & Pramanik, S. (2020). Neutrosophic simply soft open set in neutrosophic soft topological space. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 38, 235-243.
10. Das, S., & Tripathy, B.C. (2020). Pairwise neutrosophic- b -open set in neutrosophic bitopological spaces. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 38, 135-144.
11. Das, S., & Tripathy, B.C. (2021). Neutrosophic simply b -open set in neutrosophic topological spaces. *Iraqi Journal of Science*. (In Press)
12. Hasan, A.K. (2017). On intuitionistic fuzzy d -ideal of d -algebra. *Journal University of Kerbala*, 15 (1), 161-169.
13. Hasan, A.K. (2020). Intuitionistic fuzzy d -filter of d -algebra. *Journal of mechanics of continua and mathematical sciences*, 15 (6), 360-370.
14. Iami, Y., & Iseki, K. (1966). On axiom system of propositional calculi XIV. *Proceedings of the Japan Academy*, 42, 19-20.
15. Iseki, K., & Tanaka, S. (1978). An introduction to the theory of BCK-algebra. *Mathematica Japonicae*, 23 (1), 1-26.
16. Jun, Y.B., Kim, H.S., & Yoo, D.S. (e-2006). Intuitionistic fuzzy d -algebra. *Scientiae Mathematicae Japonicae Online*, e-2006, 1289–1297.
17. Jun, Y.B., Neggers, J., & Kim, H.S. (2000). Fuzzy d -ideals of d -algebras. *Journal of Fuzzy Mathematics*, 8 (1), 123-130.
18. Kadhum, H.J., & Kareem, A.H. (2018). Some types of fuzzy pseudo ideals in pseudo Q -algebra. *Thesis, Department of mathematics, University of Kufa*, pp. 1-109.
19. Kareem, A.H., & Ahmed, H.Z. (2016). Complete BCK-ideal. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 137 (3), 302-314.
20. Mallick, R., & Pramanik, S. (2020). Pentapartitioned neutrosophic set and its properties. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 36, 184-192.
21. Martina Jency, J., & Arockiarani. I. (2016). Single valued neutrosophic ideals of BCK-algebras. *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology*, 39 (1), 8-17.
22. Mostafa, S.M., Abdel Naby, M.A., & Elgendy, O.R. (2012). Fuzzy Q -ideals in Q -algebras. *World Applied Programming*, 2 (2), 69-80.
23. Mostafa, S.M., Abdel Naby, M.A., & Elgendy, O.R. (2012). Intuitionistic fuzzy Q -ideals in Q -algebra. *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 8 (2), 135-144.
24. Neggers, J., Ahn, S.S., & Kim, H.S. (2001). On Q -algebra. *International Journal of Mathematics and Mathematical Sciences*, 27 (12), 749-757.
25. Neggers, J., Jun, Y.B., & Kim, H.S. (1999). On d -ideals in d -algebras. *Mathematica Slovaca*, 49 (3), 243-251.
26. Neggers, J., & Kim, H.S. (1999). On d -algebra. *Mathematica Slovaca*, 49 (1), 19-26.
27. Smarandache, F. (2005). Neutrosophic set: a generalization of the intuitionistic fuzzy sets. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 24, 287-297.
28. Smarandache, F. (2013). n -Valued Refined Neutrosophic Logic and Its Applications in Physics, *Progress in Physics*, 4, 143-146.
29. Zadeh, L.A. (1965). Fuzzy set. *Information and Control*, 8, 338-353.

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